

*Mehriban Mammadova Oktay**Doctor of Philosophy in Philology**Ganja State University, Department of Azerbaijani Language*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15495148>**SEMANTIC FEATURES OF LITERARY STUDIES TERMS IN THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE****Summary**

Literary studies terminology constitutes a fundamental direction within the scientific terminology of the Azerbaijani language. The historical development stages of Azerbaijani terminology, marked by their ancient origins, are distinguished by specific features. Alongside the development of the literary language, its terminology also evolves.

Term formation is an integral part of the word-formation process in the language, functioning in accordance with its grammatical principles. The same principles that govern word formation in the Azerbaijani language are applied in the creation of literary studies terminology. The methods of term formation have evolved in line with the socio-political characteristics of each period. In earlier stages, lexical and grammatical elements played a more active role in term formation, but over time, they became less prominent, giving way to semantic methods as the primary source of terminological development.

Keywords: *literary criticism terminology, terminology of the Azerbaijani language, terminology creation, word formation, semantic method*

Language constitutes a powerful, significant, and indispensable medium of information within human society, facilitating the transmission of the past to the present and the present to the future. Consequently, language must be preserved and sustained. The rules governing language should be established in such a way that, even after five hundred or a thousand years, information can still be conveyed to future generations without any loss of meaning. It is imperative to develop and safeguard the linguistic norms that are universally comprehensible so that subsequent generations can understand the language without difficulty.

Ensuring the clarity of language necessitates the creation and stabilization of its corresponding norms, which represents one of the fundamental challenges in linguistic preservation. The more stable the linguistic norms, the longer their lifespan. Furthermore, the greater the longevity of these norms, the more extensive the language's capacity to serve as a medium of information.

Throughout its historical development, the Azerbaijani language has undergone both significant stages of enrichment and periods of profound external influence and pressure. The Azerbaijani language's wealth of word-formation and inflectional mechanisms, the establishment of a highly systematic suffixation process, the capacity to express multiple meanings with a limited number of words, and the existence of a distinctive sequential pattern in word order all signify that, even in ancient times, this language functioned as a highly influential medium of communication within social contexts. A language actively engaged in public life inevitably functions as a medium of information for a society characterized by robust statehood. Nevertheless, during certain historical periods, the Azerbaijani language faced intense external pressures and influences, resulting in the disruption of a unified linguistic norm, which subsequently gave way to stylistic variations of arbitrary nature.

For example, despite the ancient and rich traditions embodied in the epic tales of *Kitabi-Dədə*

Qorqud, no reliable information about written sources in the Azerbaijani language exists prior to the 13th century. The earliest known written source in Azerbaijani is currently attributed to the ghazal by Izzeddin Hasanoghlu. The first line of each couplet in the ghazal remains clearly comprehensible today, whereas the second line, densely laden with Arabic and Persian compounds, poses greater interpretative challenges. In the period following Hasanoghlu, classical traditions continued to dominate the language of Azerbaijani written literature. As a result, even today, the works of eminent poets and literary figures such as Nasimi, Fuzuli, Govsi Tabrizi, and many other illustrious authors, who have made invaluable contributions to the cultural heritage, remain difficult to fully comprehend due to their deviation from the vernacular norms.

During the independence period, the modern Azerbaijani language has developed a rich terminological lexicon encompassing various domains, including socio-political, scientific-technical, cultural-educational, and international-diplomatic fields. This terminological expansion has contributed to the comprehensive development of the Azerbaijani language in the contemporary era, enhancing and refining its lexical composition.

One of the significant branches of scientific terminology within the Azerbaijani language is literary studies terminology. The origins of Azerbaijani language terminology are rooted in antiquity. However, the systematic development of terminology predominantly occurred during the Soviet period [6, 11–17; 10, 18–23]. During this time, word formation primarily relied on the internal resources of the language, with borrowings introduced as necessary. Alongside the evolution of the literary language, its terminological system also advanced. Historically, one branch of evolving terminology that has become systematically stabilized is literary studies terminology.

The usage of literary studies terms in the Azerbaijani language dates back to the medieval period and subsequently underwent significant developmental

stages. The progress of literary studies as a discipline, the emergence of textbooks and educational resources for higher and secondary general education, as well as the creation of dictionaries, were key factors in the advancement of Azerbaijani literary studies terminology. As a result, the terminology developed, expanded, normalized, and eventually stabilized [8, 13–23].

Researchers generally attribute the formation of the Azerbaijani literary language to the 11th century, identifying the first written monument of this period as *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*. This text contains numerous literary studies terms, allowing it to be regarded as one of the earliest sources in this field.

The written period of the Azerbaijani literary language, initiated through the contributions of prominent literary figures such as Hasanoghlu, Nasimi, Khatai, Fuzuli, and Vagif, also saw the emergence of literary studies terminology within these primary texts. Additionally, Mahmud al-Kashgari's *Diwan Lughat al-Turk*, considered a fundamental source for the Azerbaijani language, contains various literary studies terms, some of which persist in contemporary Azerbaijani.

Term formation, as an integral component of the lexical development process, operates within the grammatical framework of the language. The same fundamental principles governing word formation in the Azerbaijani language are applied in the creation of literary studies terms. According to M. Mammadov, the methods and sources of term formation are adapted to the socio-political context of each historical period. For instance, lexical and grammatical elements that once played an active role in term formation may later become less prominent, or a primary source of term creation may be replaced by another [7, 16].

Studies on term formation outline the following methods of term creation:

1. Semantic Method;
2. Morphological Method;
3. Syntactic Method;
4. Calque Method [5, 23–31].

To designate new objects and phenomena, various methods are employed, one of which involves assigning a new meaning to an existing word or term. This approach results not in a quantitative increase but in a qualitative enhancement of terminology. In this case, the internal structure of the term remains unchanged, but it acquires a new conceptual dimension due to a semantic shift. Essentially, the new concept or object establishes an associative link with a pre-existing concept or object, thereby extending the meaning of the term. Consequently, the new concept is expressed through existing words, augmenting the semantic load of the term [6, 91–92].

In Azerbaijani, the semantic method plays a significant role in the formation of literary studies terms across various scientific fields. Terms formed through the semantic method acquire additional terminological meanings as a result of semantic evolution, thus becoming terminological units. The word formation process via the semantic method manifests in specific contexts, including:

1. The terminologization of certain colloquial words;

2. The specialization of meaning;
3. The semantic broadening of a word [5, 123].

Historical-comparative research demonstrates that most terms have emerged through the semantic evolution of either Turkic-origin words or borrowed words. In Azerbaijani, literary studies terms formed through the semantic method include the terminologization of certain colloquial words (e.g., *ağı*, *bayatı*, *varsağı*, *tuyuq*), as well as the specialization of one of a word's meanings, which then transforms into a term (e.g., *qol*, *boy*, *zırvə*, *dastan*). S. Guliyeva points out that "there are no literary studies terms in Azerbaijani formed through semantic broadening."

The *Dictionary of Literary Studies Terms* states that in ancient Azerbaijan, mourning for a great hero was a customary practice. On the day of the hero's death, people would gather in a communal space referred to as "yuq." The *uğçu* (the mourner) would first extol the hero's virtues, followed by a transition to a mournful melody, singing laments for the celebrated hero [2, 7].

The term *ağı* was a widely used lexical unit in the traditional lifestyle of Azerbaijanis. Initially a colloquial term, it later evolved into a scientific-literary concept, thus becoming a term. The word *ağı* is predominantly used in Azerbaijani literary studies [2, 7], though it occasionally appears in Turkmen literary studies as well.

In Mahmud al-Kashgari's renowned work *Diwan Lughat al-Turk*, the word *yığ/yuğ* is recorded with meanings such as "to cry," "mourning," "tear," and "meal served at a mourning ceremony." Over time, one of the meanings of the ancient word *ağı* became specialized, specifically referring to a song sung at mourning ceremonies, ultimately solidifying as a term within literary studies. In Azerbaijani, derivatives of this term include *ağı-çı* (lamerter) and *ağıcı sözlər* (lamerter words).

Terms Arising from Semantic Specialization

Terms formed through semantic specialization emerge from the narrowing of a word's meaning. One prominent example in folklore studies is the term *aşiq*. In ancient Azerbaijani tradition, the term *aşiq* was preceded by names like *ozan*, *varsaq*, and *yanşaq* [2, 17–18].

M.H. Təhmasib, discussing the etymology of the word *aşiq*, asserts that it does not derive from the Arabic word *aşiq* (lover) but from the Turkic verb *aşılamaq* (to play music). He posits that the root *aş* could have transformed into *aşiq* by adopting the suffix *-iq* in accordance with the phonological rules of the Azerbaijani language, forming a noun or title [10, 41].

The word *aşiq* is polysemous, recorded in ancient Turkic written monuments with meanings such as "chicken bone" and "helmet" (DTS, p. 64), and also appearing in M. Kashgari's dictionary with the same meanings. In the epic *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*, *aşiq* denotes both "a gaming piece" and "helmet" [10, 27]. According to the *Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language*, *aşiq* also signifies "folk singer," "game piece," "game name," "knucklebone," and "the metallic

part between the hammer and the foot of a rifle" [8, 166]. In modern Azerbaijani, *aşıq* remains widely used.

Lexical Units Arising from Semantic Specialization in Literature

Another example of a lexical unit derived from semantic specialization is the term *boy*. In folklore studies, *boy* denotes a part of an epic or a chapter dedicated to a specific event, historically referring to a segment of Turkic oral literature (Literary Studies Terms Dictionary, p. 30).

The *Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language* provides five meanings for the word *boy*:

1. Body height;
2. Length;
3. Elevation or height;
4. Magnitude;
5. A chapter or section of an epic.

The fifth meaning reflects the terminological semantics of *boy* [6, 301-302]. Written monuments of Azerbaijani also contain the terminological sense of *boy*. For instance, in *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*, the word *boy* signifies "epic" (Oghuzname), as in: "*Dirsə xan oğlu Buğacan boyunu bəyan edər*" (Dirsa Khan's son Bugachan tells his epic). Additionally, the expression "*Dədə Qorqud boy boyladı, soy söylədi...*" also uses *boy* in the context of an epic chapter [9, 30].

Historically, the term *boy* also denoted "tribe" in ancient Turkic written sources (DTS, p. 110), a usage noted by Kashgari with the marking *Oghuzca*. In *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*, the word also appears in the sense of "tribe," as in: "... *Bayat boyundan Qorqud Ata derlər bir ər qopdu*" (From the Bayat tribe, a hero named Dədə Qorqud emerged) [9, 14].

The Term *Qol* in Literary Studies

One of the terminological units formed through semantic specialization in modern Azerbaijani is the word *qol*. In folklore studies, *qol* refers to interconnected parts of Azerbaijani epic tales. For example, the *Koroğlu* epic consists of multiple *qols* (branches). M. Kashgari's dictionary records the word *qol* in the same sense as used in modern Azerbaijani.

Thus, the literary studies term *qol* developed from one of the historical meanings of the polysemous word *qol*. An example of usage: "*In recent years, several new branches (qol) of the Koroğlu epic have been collected*" [3, 251]. According to the *Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language*, *qol* has eight meanings, with the fifth being the terminological one: "a part, chapter, or story of an epic" [6, 339-340].

Semantic Differentiation in Dialect Usage

The word *suç* (crime or fault) is used in the dialects of Gadabay, Tovuz, and Jabrayil to mean "guilt" or "fault" (4, p. 163). Its subsequent semantic change has led to its differentiation and specialization as a legal term in modern Turkish, where *suç* and its derivatives are predominantly used in legal contexts. In Azerbaijani, however, *suç* remains localized, appearing mainly

in fairy tales, epics, and other folklore texts. The prevalence of the Persian loanword *günah* (sin) in the Azerbaijani language has somewhat overshadowed the native term *suç*.

Although the assimilation of such archaic elements into modern usage is challenging, identifying and rehabilitating these native words as synonymous variants through the analysis of ancient linguistic examples is both feasible and necessary.

Although such lexical units do not differ in form from their counterparts in the "Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud," they may vary in meaning. These differences manifest as both semantic shifts and simple changes in meaning. Semantic narrowing is accompanied by a reduction in the semantic scope of the word. As the narrowing deepens, it leads to a qualitative change, resulting in a new semantic variant that differs from the previous one.

In "Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud," the word *aş* signifies "food." For instance: "*Həm ölümlərimiz üçün verdiyimiz aş əllərindən çəkib alub yeyər imiş*" ("He used to take and eat the *aş* that we offered for our deceased"). In modern Azerbaijani, however, the general meaning of "food" has disappeared, and the word has stabilized, specifically denoting only one type of dish (*pilaf*). A similar development pattern can be observed in other Turkic languages. In Tatar and Bashkir, the word *aş* signifies "grain."

The differences in meaning observed when comparing some words from the text of "Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud" with their equivalents in modern Turkic languages cannot be attributed solely to historical and temporal distance. Several factors underlie this divergence. First, following the compilation of the work, the differentiation within the Common Turkic unity occurred, leading to the emergence of distinct areas. Over time, each area began to exhibit unique features. Subsequently, as interethnic differentiation took place, distinctive traditions emerged in social life, daily practices, ethical relations, and the socio-cultural environment. Naturally, this process led to the emergence of new concepts within each social environment.

In terms of linguistic structure, the established tradition of preserving relevant meanings within new semantic frameworks has existed since ancient times. Therefore, new concepts within the language often entail the expression of corresponding meanings through new compositional structures. Although this tradition limits word formation within the language, it is a universal phenomenon, characteristic not only of Turkic languages but of all languages. The important point here is to determine concepts based on the same analytical framework rather than conducting isolated etymological analyses of individual words. Such an approach in etymological analysis is significant as it helps prevent erroneous conclusions by the researcher.

Words that have undergone semantic changes, despite maintaining the same form as in "Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud," may differ in meaning. These differences manifest as either semantic transformations or simple changes in meaning. Semantic narrowing is accompanied by a reduction in the semantic boundaries of the word. As narrowing becomes more profound, it results in a qualitative change, giving rise to a distinct semantic specification that differs from the original.

In the earliest example of our written literary language, *Dastani-Əhməd Hərami*, literary studies terminology from the formative and initial developmental period of Azerbaijani literary language can be observed, including terms such as *qopuz*, *saz*, *qissə*, *hekayət*, *vəsf-i-hal*, and *dastan*. Notably, the word *dastan* in the title does not denote a genre but is used in the sense of "event," "tale," or "narrative." In the works of Nasir al-Din Tusi, one can also find explanations of several literary terms such as *content*, *form*, *tragedy*, *comedy*, and others.

The lexicon of Nasimi's works is remarkably rich and contains numerous literary studies terms. Linguistic evidence indicates that most of the literary terms used in Nasimi's works are of Arabic-Persian origin, including *əfsanə* (legend), *məcaz* (metaphor), *nəzm* (verse), *nəğmə* (song), *təşbeh* (simile), *qissə* (tale), *qissəxan* (storyteller), *qəsidə* (ode), *şeyr* (poem), *rəvayət* (narrative), *divan* (collection of poems), *dastan* (epic), and *hekayət* (story), among others.

The term *yazıçı* (writer), of Azerbaijani origin, appears for the first time in Nasimi's works. In Nasimi's texts, the term *yazıçı* is employed in the same sense as in modern literary studies. For example:

Do not consider the truth to be false, do not say there is no truth,

The writer writes, do not say there is no page.

(Nasimi, "Divani", p. 542).

The term *yazıçı* has remained unchanged both semantically and phonetically from the 14th century to the present, maintaining its original meaning in modern Azerbaijani.

Nasimi's lyrical and scientific-philosophical poems played a significant role in the development of the 14th-century Azerbaijani literary language and in the formation of literary studies and Hurufi terminology.

The Scientific Dimension of Fuzuli's Language

Following Nasimi, the scientific level of Azerbaijani poetic language is primarily associated with Fuzuli. The main characteristic of Fuzuli's language is its scholarly and philosophical nature. This scholarly quality is not limited to his philosophical reflections or his generalizations about life and society, nor solely to his use of scientific-philosophical terminological vocabulary, but also manifests in the way he expresses his thoughts.

In Fuzuli's works, one finds the use of various literary terms, including *qəzəl* (ghazal), *mahnı* (song), *qafiyə* (rhyme), *nəzm* (verse), *nəzim* (poet), *şair* (poet), *nəsir* (prose), *şairlik* (poetry), *məsnəvi* (mesnevi), *divan* (poetry collection), *surət* (image), *üslub* (style), *beyt* (couplet), *zərbiül-məsəl* (proverb), *ibarə* (expression), and *dibaçə* (preface).

A notable example from Fuzuli's poetry illustrates the significance of the *qəzəl* form:

A ghazal is the crystal that brings pleasure to the enlightened,

A ghazal is the rose in the garden of art...

A ghazal reveals the poet's talent,

A ghazal enhances the fame of the poet (Nazim). (Fuzuli, I, p. 44).

The Arabic-origin term *qəzəl* in the given example denotes "lyric poetry." This terminological meaning remains unchanged to the present day.

The period following Fuzuli represents a distinct phase in the development of Azerbaijani literary language, particularly regarding the evolution of Azerbaijani language terminology. During the late 16th and early 17th centuries, the literary language increasingly incorporated lexical units, expressions, and grammatical structures from the vernacular language. At this stage, alongside Arabic-Persian origin terms, Azerbaijani literary terminology also featured lexical units that emerged from the intrinsic linguistic resources of the Azerbaijani language.

In the 17th and 18th centuries, literary terminology displayed a dual character: on one hand, it retained classical Eastern poetic terms, while on the other, it incorporated unique terms characteristic of Azerbaijani literature itself. A significant portion of the literary terminology used during the 17th and 18th centuries is found in the works of M.P. Vagif. Notably, Vagif's texts contain literary terms such as *qəzəl* (ghazal), *bayatı* (bayati), and *müxəmməs* (mukhammas), which have retained their semantic consistency.

Conclusion

The semantic analysis of literary terminology in the Azerbaijani language demonstrates that the rapid development of literary studies in recent years has led to the emergence of various terminological systems related to its diverse fields. The ongoing evolution of the discipline and the accelerated progress of literary studies in the new stage necessitate addressing issues such as terminological parallelism, inaccuracies in meaning representation within terminological dictionaries, terminological ambiguities, and other standardization challenges.

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